

A Rare Case of Arterio-Venous Malformation with Invasive Mole**Nidhi Kumari¹, Shanu Prakash², Swapan Kumar Kundu³, Soumyajyoti Kundu⁴**^{1,2}Junior Resident, Dept of OBGYN, MGM Medical College, Kishanganj, Bihar³Professor, Dept of OBGYN, MGM Medical College, Kishanganj, Bihar⁴Junior Resident, Dept of Microbiology, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Haldia, W. Bengal

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Arterio-Venous Malformations and Invasive Mole rarely coexist causing Heavy and Irregular Uterine Bleeding. One such multigravida attended OBGYN Emergency dept. with a previous h/o Dilatation and Evacuation of uterus. Beta hCG was raised. TVS suggested AV Malformation and uterine artery aneurysm and suspected Placental Site Trophoblastic Tumor. PAP smear showed Negative for any Intraepithelial Lesion or Malignancy. Histo-pathology report of Hysterectomy specimen showed Invasive Mole. Follow up serial beta hCG levels after TAH BSO showed gradual decline and by 6 months it was undetectable.

Keywords: Arterio-Venous Malformations, Invasive Mole, Beta hCG, Gestational Trophoblastic Disease, Abnormal Uterine Bleeding, Uterine Curettage, Histo-pathology.

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Introduction

An Invasive Mole is a Gestational Trophoblastic Disease (GTD) that penetrates and may even perforate uterine wall. Uterine Arterio-Venous Malformation (UAVM) is known as a direct connection of the arterial system to the venous system, without contribution of capillary vessels. This vascular abnormality is rare as the review of literature shows the incidence UAVM is 0.10%. [1] This malformation is considered as local or generalized lesions. UAVM classifies to congenital and acquired. Occurrence of acquired UAVM is more common than congenital type that resulted from some situations such as "Gestational Trophoblastic Disease, pelvic trauma, surgical procedures (cesarean section, curettage), cervical or endometrial carcinoma, infection and exposure to diethylstilbestrol". If both the conditions appear together then it may lead to Abnormal Uterine Bleeding (AUB). [2]

Case Presentation

A G₅P₃L₃A₁ female aged 46 years attended Emergency OBGYN department with complaints of frequent irregular bleeding per vagina since last 11 months due to which she has already received two units of blood transfusions in another hospital. She had previous three vaginal deliveries, 13 years 12

years and 10 years back, with a history of spontaneous miscarriage 11 months back which was followed by Dilatation and Evacuation (D&E).

Per abdomen, uterus was just palpable. Per vaginal examination revealed uterus was 12 weeks size with os closed and bleeding present on examining finger. [3]

Her urinary pregnancy test report came out to be positive, beta hCG level raised to 1353.7 mIU/ml, on the day of 1st visit. [4]

Transvaginal and Transabdominal Ultrasonography pictures showed:

1. Multiple vascular channels predominantly in fundus and body region of anterior myometrium with anechoic cystic pockets showing turbulent flow suggesting AV Malformation and uterine artery aneurysm.
2. Irregular echogenic soft tissue lesion at anterior endo-myometrial interface which showed no internal vascularity which raises suspicion of Placental Site Trophoblastic Tumor (PSTT) or GTD.

The patient had been admitted. After consultation with all faculty members and considering her age of 46 years, decision taken for hysterectomy with removal of adnexae. Her routine pre-operative investigations were done which were within normal limits, including O-positive blood group. Her TSH was raised for which levothyroxine was started and her serum beta hCG showed 1290.0 mIU/ml just

pre-op. PAP smear showed Negative for any Intraepithelial Lesion or Malignancy (NILM). Total Abdominal Hysterectomy with Bilateral Salpingo-Oophorectomy (TAH BSO) was done. Uterine specimen was bulky. Cut specimen showed reddish brown fleshy mass at endo-myometrial junction. Cervix, tubes, ovaries looked normal.

Figure 1: Operative Specimen

Figure 2:

The whole specimen was sent for Histo-Pathological Examination (HPE).

Patient was followed up with serial beta hCG which showed 224.0 mIU/ml on 1st post-op day of TAH

BSO, thereafter weekly serum beta hCG showed 13.4 mIU/ml in first week and 1.0 mIU/ml in second week, after this serial beta hCG done monthly till 6 months which was almost undetectable.

Figure 3: Dilated and Hyalinised Chorionic Villi deep into Myometrium

Her H/P report showed:

1. Invasive mole
2. Proliferative endometrium
3. Chronic nonspecific cervicitis
4. Left ovarian corpus luteal cyst

Figure 4: Proliferation of Trophoblastic Cells of Epithelioid morphology with areas of Haemorrhage

Discussion

Uterine AVM can be serious persistent cause of vaginal bleeding. Attempt to do uterine curettage may lead to torrential uncontrolled bleeding leading to haemorrhagic shock, a real threat to patient's life. Definitive treatment option is Hysterectomy and as she was >45years, ovaries were removed. [5]

2. Treatment of Invasive mole is TAH, and patients should be followed up with weekly serial beta hCG estimation till it becomes negative and thereafter every monthly till 6 months to check the effectiveness of the treatment and to check whether the disease has converted to malignancy. [6,7]

Conclusion

AV Malformation with Invasive mole is a very rare condition and proper investigations should be done to reach provisional diagnosis, plan treatment and counsel patient for follow up. HPE is necessary to confirm the diagnosis and exclude any malignancy and need for further chemotherapy. This patient might have GTD 11 months back, but Beta hCG was not done, product was not examined for HPE and there were no follow ups. Persistent vaginal bleeding may also be due to concurrent AV Malformation.

Author Contributions: All authors are involved in diagnosing and treatment, including operation, while the corresponding author wrote the case report. All authors contributed to data analysis, literature review, drafting or revising the article, gave final approval of the version to be published, agreed to the journal submitted, and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Informed Consent: Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for their anonymized information to be published in this article.

Patient Consent: Informed written consent has been obtained from the patient for all case details and images to be reported in the journal.

Financial Disclosure: The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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